

Phytochemical Study of *Cassia siamea*

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*Manuscript received 10 October 1990, revised 1 January 1991,
accepted 24 April 1991*

C*ASSIA siamea* (Lam.) is a fast growing tree¹. Its aerial parts have shown to be diuretic². Although several workers have gone through its phytochemistry³ but the roots are still less investigated and is limited only to the presence of bianthraquinones⁴. This tempted us to reinvestigate the roots of the plant. Here we report the isolation of a rutinoid of 1-hydroxy-6,8-dimethoxy-2-methyl-anthraquinone.

The ethanolic extract of the roots (10 kg) was distributed into different organic layers of increasing polarity. On chromatography of the ethyl acetate extract fraction on a column of silica gel, the rutinoid in impure form was obtained. It was purified again on similar column and crystallised from ethyl acetate.

The glycoside showed the absence of 1,4-dihydroxysystem⁵ and was insoluble in 5% sodium carbonate⁶ indicating the absence of β -hydroxyl functions but responded the positive colour test with copper sulphate⁷ indicating the free α -hydroxyl group (also clear in the uv data). Since these tests were performed well by the aglycone hence the only possibility of the glycosilation was at position-3. The usual procedures for establishing the structure of glycoside were made as in our previous paper⁸ and the structure assigned was thus 1-hydroxy-6,8-dimethoxy-2-methylantraquinone-3-O-rutinoside.

The glycoside revealed, m.p. 122° (Found : C, 47.10; H, 4.70. Calcd. for : C, 47.15; H, 4.61%); $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 222, 250, 373 and 440 nm; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 340, 2 950, 2 890, 1 720, 1 670, 1 650, 1 450, 1 180 and 730 cm^{-1} ; pmr δ (CDCl_3 , 250 MHz) 0.98 (3H, br, rhamnose methyl), 2.10 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.85 (6H, s, OCH_3), 3.40–4.84 (10H, br, sugar protons), 5.00 (1H, s, H-1''), 5.25 (1H, s, H-1' glucosyl), 6.85 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-7), 7.68 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-5) and 7.80 (1H, s, H-4) ppm.

The hydrolysis of the glycoside (150 mg) with 7% H_2SO_4 afforded an aglycone (m.p. 272°) along with glucose and rhamnose in equimolecular ratio; the aglycone, δ (CDCl_3 ; 90 MHz) 7.90 (1H, s, H-4), 7.65 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-5), 6.80 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-7), 3.90 (6H, s, OCH_3), 2.10 (3H, s, CH_3); m/z 314 (M^+), 296, 286, 268, 240, 212, 136 and 76, and it was identified as 1,3-dihydroxy-6,8-dimethoxy-2-methylantraquinone.

Interestingly, this rutinoside has been reported to be present in the same part of *Cassia marginata*⁹. Its occurrence and the presence of two other anthraquinone rutinosides from *Cassia*^{10,11} genus may again be significant if it is correlated with the most widespread occurring rutin. A very limited work has been made in the field of anthraquinone glycosides^{1,2}.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank their Principals for facilities, Pennsylvania State University, U.S.A. for pmr data, Director, C.D.R.I., Lucknow for other spectral analysis and Dr. H. P. Tewari, Head of the Chemistry Department, University of Allahabad for valuable discussion.

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